

A HEURISTIC METHOD FOR MODELLING THE SLIDING RESISTANCE OF MASONRY ASSEMBLAGES OF INTERLOCKING BLOCKS

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Abstract

There is a wealth of recent literature dealing with the significant role played by friction in the seismic response of conventional masonry structures. Within this framework, a crafty improvement of such structures is represented by interlocking masonry structures made by interlocking blocks that enhance the sliding resistance at block interfaces. In fact, these are rigid block units which, on their faces, have a number of locks keeping the blocks together and preventing sliding. Such typologies of blocks can increase the structural functionality of an assemblage during and after the construction. The interlocking interface may have different sliding resistances in different directions, depending on the orientation and the mechanical and geometrical features of the locks. This paper is aimed at finding the sliding resistance of interlocking interfaces with non-isotropic sliding properties. The constraint is a function of geometric and mechanical properties of such interfaces, allowing the use of the convex contact formulation method to analyse the structural behaviour of masonry assemblages composed of interlocking blocks.

Keywords: Interlocking Blocks, Non-Isotropic Sliding Resistance, Shear Resistance, Convex Contact Formulation, Discrete Model, Coulomb's Friction Law, Limit Analysis Theory.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural modelling of the discontinuous nature of assemblages of rigid blocks have been pursued using finite element analysis (FEA), discrete element analysis (DEA), and limit analysis theories, among others. FE methods modelled masonry as connected or distinct elements with different material properties for bricks and mortar joints (detailed and simplified micro models respectively) [1]. In DE methods, masonry was modelled as a system of distinct blocks for which the equations of motion are solved using an explicit time integration method [2]. Discrete modelling is also used with macro-element approaches [3,4].

Contact formulation using limit analysis theory [5] is less computationally expensive comparing to FE and DE methods, yet highly accurate to analyse the structural feasibility of rigid block assemblages. Particularly, defining a set of limiting conditions allows this method to calculate the ultimate load factor for a structurally feasible assemblage of rigid blocks satisfying static and kinematic conditions.

In particular, concave or point contact formulation is a dominant approach to model stress state of assemblages of rigid blocks, first developed by Livesley [6]. In this method, the contact interfaces are idealized so that the internal forces are distributed on a few contact points on the contact interfaces. Instead, convex contact formulation represents the interaction between blocks via the stress state at a single point on their interface [7]. For both formulations, a set of limit state formulations can be developed guaranteeing that when the obtained internal forces are within the limiting range, the assemblage is structurally feasible. These limiting conditions, including infinite compressive and no tensile strengths, infinite [8] or finite sliding resistance with associative [5,6] or non-associative [9,10] frictional resistance, were developed for conventional interfaces with isotropic sliding properties. Pseudo-non-associative frictional law is also considered in non-smooth contact dynamics models recently developed for complex systems of conventional rigid blocks in frictional contact [11,12].

To increase the in-plane and out-of-plane capacity of walls, proper interlocking or semi-interlocking connections among blocks can be used [13-19]. When using these kinds of blocks, the limiting conditions for interfaces in masonry assemblages, with non-isotropic sliding properties (different sliding resistance in different directions/locations of the interface) should be properly defined, along with constraints in function of geometric properties of the interlocking interfaces (Figure 1.a).

Figure 1. a) interlocking blocks and their geometric parameters determining the sliding resistance, b) concave approach extension for the interlocking interfaces.

The authors of this paper are currently developing a novel approach to extend the concave contact formulation to the corrugated interlocking interfaces subjected to any types of external forces and torques. This approach suits the non-isotropic nature of the interlocking interface problem, since the contact points are chosen so that the mechanical behaviour of every lock of an interlocking interface can be thoroughly studied along different directions. In particular, the end points of each lock centreline are considered the contact points (Figure 1.b). Then the

stress resultants at these points are computed by solving the equilibrium problem under: (a) shear constraints avoiding the shear/torsional cracking of the locks, (b) friction constraint avoiding sliding along the locks and (c) compressive constraint avoiding the block separation/rocking.

In this paper, however, the attention is only focused on the convex contact formulation for interlocking interfaces subjected to the lateral and normal forces. This is the first step to be accomplished since the convex formulation provides more reliable results than the concave one [7]. In particular, a heuristic method is presented to find the sliding resistance of the interlocking interfaces. In the following, the 2D interlocking interfaces having locks with rectangular cross section (Figure 2.a) is first studied. Then, a conservative method to formulate the contact behaviour of the 3D quadrilateral interfaces composed of locks with rectangular cross section (Figure 2.b) is developed.

Figure 2. a) An interlocking 2D and b) 3D interface subjected to the lateral and normal forces.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 2D limit analysis model

A 2D limit analysis model is applicable to the 3D assemblages in which both the applied forces and structural model can be abstracted to a 2D plane, e.g. a masonry flat wall subjected to the in-plane forces. By implementing the interlocking blocks, it is assumed that all the locks are oriented normally to this plane.

First the potential failure lines can be assumed for an interlocking block, e.g. the red dashed lines displayed in Figure 3.a. The structural model then consists of rigid bodies whose boundaries are these failure lines, where internal forces are distributed on. The failure lines include dry joints between two interlocking blocks (blue lines) and fracture lines at which the block might crack (red lines).

In this paper, it is assumed that the fracture is avoided at red dashed lines of Figure 3.a, by considering the main body of the interlocking block rigid enough. The remaining active failure lines all together form an interlocking interface. In the following, the sliding resistance of such an interface, subjected to the tangential and normal forces, is analyzed.

Considering a rigid perfectly-plastic behaviour of the blocks, the potential fracture line can be cracked when tension or shear resistance is not enough (Figure 3.b). Assuming a uniform horizontal force distribution on a single lock, torsion is avoided, yet the joint might crack because of shear or bending failure. In this paper, the bending failure is prevented, by considering stocky locks with thickness s larger than height h (Figure 3.b). Later this constraint will be proved.

Figure 3. a) Potential failure lines including fracture lines (red) and dry joints (blue); b) and c) force distribution and bending and shear failure of a lock.

Assuming the structural model of a lock, the force per unit length at every point of the lock t_b must be less than the yielding force t_y . When the force is distributed uniformly, the limiting value for the resultant of the forces on a lock ($t_b b$), where b is length of the lock (Figure 3.b, c), becomes $(t_y b)$, i.e. the pure limiting shear force. Knowing the resultant of horizontal forces on an interlocking interface T_R , Inequality (1) presents the shear constraint for all potential fracture lines of an interface:

$$\begin{cases} T_i \leq t_y b \quad \forall i \in \text{locks} \\ A_{res} \cdot T - T_R = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where T_i is the horizontal force applied to lock i , T is a vector of forces on the locks T_1 to T_m , m is the total number of locks (e.g. $m = 5$ in Figure 3.b, c), A_{res} is resultant equation matrix.

Since the resultant equation can be written as a scalar addition $T_R = \sum T_i$, all constraints for m locks can be generalized as:

$$T_R \leq m t_y b = T_y \quad (2)$$

t_y depends on the lock thickness s , the material shear strength τ_k , and the normal force imposed on the lock. With reference to the latter, generally the shear resistance of a lock which is subjected to shear and compressive forces is greater than the shear resistance of a lock which is only subjected to pure shear forces, because of the effect of the compression. However, for the sake of safety and to make t_y independent of the normal force, the pure shear resistance is assumed as limiting value, neglecting the contribution of the compressive forces.

On the other hand, as introduced earlier, stocky locks with $h \leq s$ can be considered to avoid bending failure. This constraint is found according to the classical Jourawski and Navier formulas [20], respectively assuming the limiting shear force $T_{i,y}$ and bending moment $M_{i,y}$ for a single lock i to be:

$$T_i \leq T_{i,y} = t_y b = \frac{2}{3} \tau_k s b \quad T_i \frac{h}{2} \leq M_{i,y} = \frac{1}{6} f_{tk} b s^2 \quad (3)$$

where τ_k and f_{tk} are the shear and tensile strengths of the material, respectively. To define a simple, yet conservative results, we assume that $\tau_k = (0.5 f_{tk})$ (as in case of pure shear and ac-

according to the Tresca yield criterion [21]). To make shear failure to occur before bending failure, the following constraint must be satisfied:

$$T_i \leq \frac{2}{3} \tau_k sb \leq \frac{1}{6h} f_{tk} bs^2 \quad (4)$$

from which the assumed inequality $h \leq s$ can be derived.

Considering m to be odd, in order to define the resultant shear resistance as a sum of pure shear resistances of the locks, different heights of the locks are assumed, i.e. one of two interlocked blocks has $(m-1)/2$ locks and the other has $(m+1)/2$ locks (Figure 4). In this case, it is easy to derive that whatever of them has shorter locks, shear resistance is the same and failure occurs on potential fracture lines of a same level simultaneously. In fact, the shear resistance of the interlocking blocks for both conditions is:

$$T_y = \frac{m-1}{2} T_{i,y} = \frac{m-1}{3} \tau_k sb \quad (5)$$

On the other side, a tensionless dry joint can be separated when subjected to the tension forces and it can also fail when Coulomb friction constraint is violated ($T_i \leq T_f = \mu N_i$). So, the sliding constraint finally is:

$$T_R \leq \max(T_y, T_f) \quad (6)$$

where $N = \sum N_i$.

However, as long as the total horizontal force T_R is less than the shear resistance T_y , the dry joint cannot move even though the friction constraint is violated, since the frictional resistance is generally much lower than the shear resistance.

Figure 4. Shear resistance of an interlocking interface, when the block with a) $(m-1)/2$ and b) $(m+1)/2$ locks has the shorter locks.

2.2 3D limit analysis model

An extension of the 2D model to 3D limit analysis model is presented in this section. As for the 2D model, among all the potential failure planes, only the potential fracture faces at the joints between the locks and the block main body are considered. Dry joints between the blocks are assumed as well. A potential fracture face fails when its shear resistance is violated, while the bending failure is avoided by considering $h \leq s$.

Unlike the 2D model, horizontal forces normal to a lock are also assumed to be non-uniformly distributed. As explained in Section 2.1, if the force is uniformly distributed on lock i , its limiting value is $T_{i,y} = (t_y b)$. The limiting value for the resultant of non-uniformly distributed forces, instead, is less than $(t_y b)$. The reason is that, for the sake of admissibility, only the maximum values of the force per unit length may attain the yielding t_y .

If we consider a linear force distribution (Figure 5), a conservative constraint is defined that limits the maximum value of the distributed force per unit length t_{max} to be less than or equal to the yielding force per unit length t_y . t_{max} is linearly related to t_{uni} which represents the force per unit length when force is uniformly distributed, i.e.:

$$t_{max} = k t_{uni} \quad (7)$$

where k is a coefficient in function of eccentricity d . Thus, the limiting value of T_i^n (in terms of shear resistance) would be $T_i^n \leq (t_y b_i / k_i)$, where n indicates the normal direction. The moment $(T_i^n d)$ must also be less than the torsional resistance of the lock subjected to forces with eccentric resultant. This issue, however, is out of scope of this paper.

Figure 5. Linear force distribution on a single 3D lock.

Knowing the resultant of tangential forces T_R and its location, together with its components T_R^n and T_R^t normal and parallel to the locks, respectively, an option for distribution of T_R^n among all locks is represented in Figure 6.a, b. By analogy with the 2D model, the shear resistance for all potential fracture planes of an interlocking interface is given by:

$$\begin{cases} T_i^n \leq \frac{t_y b_i}{k_i} & \forall i \in \text{locks} \\ A_{res} \cdot T^n - T_R^n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and since the resultant equation is a scalar addition $T_R^n = \sum T_i^n$, the shear constraint can be generalized as:

$$T_R^n \leq t_y \sum \frac{b_i}{k_i} \quad (9)$$

As for the 2D model, t_y can be independent of normal forces when the locks of one block are shorter than the locks of the other block. Thus, the shear constraint can be represented by:

$$T_R^n \leq \frac{2}{3} \tau_{ks} \sum \frac{b_i}{k_i} \quad (10)$$

where b_i is the length of the i^{th} shorter lock.

On the other side, as long as Inequality (10) is satisfied, a dry joint can slide along the lock when the Coulomb friction constraint is violated ($T_i^t \leq \mu N_i$), where, T_i^t is the component of tangential force parallel to the lock i . The constraint can be generalized for all the dry joints as $T_R^t \leq T_f = \mu N$, where $T_R^t = \sum T_i^t$ and $N = \sum N_i$.

Knowing the angle α between the tangential force T_R and the locks (Figure 6.c), the sliding constraint of an interlocking interface as long as the locks are not fractured is:

$$\begin{cases} T_R \sin \alpha \leq \frac{2}{3} \tau_{ks} \sum \frac{b_i}{k_i} \\ T_R \cos \alpha \leq T_f \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Once all the connectors are separated from the main body, the interface is turned to be a conventional interface. Thus, the sliding resistance can be formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} T_R \leq \frac{2\tau_{ks}}{3 \sin \alpha} \sum \frac{b_i}{k_i} \rightarrow T_R \leq \frac{\mu N}{\cos \alpha} \\ T_R \geq \frac{2\tau_{ks}}{3 \sin \alpha} \sum \frac{b_i}{k_i} \rightarrow T_R \leq \mu N \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Figure 6. a) Component of the tangential resultant normal to the locks and b) an option for its distribution among all locks. c) Tangential resultant with its components normal and parallel to the locks.

3 DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we compare the two non-linear inequalities developed for 2D and 3D interlocking models.

For the 2D model, the locks are assumed normal to the lateral forces. According to Inequality (6), if shear resistance is greater than the frictional resistance ($T_y > T_f$) the ultimate lat-

eral force will be $T_R = T_y$ because once the locks are fractured, the frictional resistance is not enough to prevent sliding. This condition, implying non-ductile behaviour of the interface, is represented by the upper black dot in Figure 7.a, where the assumed constant graph of shear resistance is located above the cohesionless Coulomb yielding point. In contrast, if $T_y < T_f$ the lateral force will be governed by T_f and ductile behaviour, since the friction resistance keeps the fractured locks on the block main body (Figure 7.b). It can be concluded that the feasible range of values for T_R and N_R is the grey zone in Figure 7.c.

Figure 7. Non-linear sliding constraint for a 2D interlocking interface, with a) $T_y > T_f$ and b) $T_y < T_f$. c) Yield domain in normal-shear interaction.

Applying Inequality (12), the 2D interlocking interface can be seen as a 3D interface on which the angle between the resultant of subjected forces and the locks α is 90 degrees. Moreover, the force on each lock is uniformly distributed, so that k_i equals one.

When α changes, the feasible range of values for T_R and N_R varies as shown in Figure 8, which shows how the graph of feasible solutions changes between two extremes for α , zero and 90 degrees.

Figure 8. Non-linear sliding constraint for a 3D interlocking interface.

4 CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

The paper introduced a sliding constraint applicable for extension of convex contact formulation to 2D interlocking interfaces, further extended to 3D interlocking interfaces. The constraints were developed according to the non-isotropic nature of the interlocking interfaces, in functions of the block geometric and mechanical properties. The width, height, length and orientation of the locks along with the shear resistance of the material and friction coefficient of the contact face are the main parameters.

Two different conditions were considered for the contact formulations: first, when the tangential forces normal to the locks are less than the shear resistance of the locks. In this case, the sliding resistance is orthotropic so that it is governed by Coulomb's model of friction along the direction parallel to the locks and by shear resistance of the locks in the direction normal to them; second, when shear resistance of the locks is very low and therefore all the locks can crack and separate from the main body of the block. This turns an interlocking interface to an isotropic conventional interface whose sliding resistance is governed by Coulomb's model of friction if the frictional resistance is greater than the shear one.

Future work, which is in progress, will focus on the non-uniform distribution of forces on locks, adding the torsional constraints to the contact formulation. The analytical results will be validated and calibrated through experimental investigations.

Beside the convex contact formulation, the concave contact formulation will also be extended to interlocking blocks, and then both approaches will be compared in terms of accuracy, comprehensiveness, and computational costs. Further interlocking geometries such as corrugated interfaces with locks having trapezoidal, sinusoidal, etc., cross sections will be analyzed by means of the more potential solution procedure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 791235. It reflects only the authors' view and the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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